

The importance of research data management (RDM)

Definition of Research Data Management (RDM)

Research Data Management (RDM) = series of measures that need to be taken during a research project in order to:

1. Obtain high-quality data
2. Make the data available and usable over the long-term
3. Make research findings reproducible beyond the research project

Benefits of good RDM for researchers

Visibility 				
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Consequences of poor RDM

Lack of reproducibility 	
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Retraction Watch:

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→ <https://retractionwatch.com/>

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